

Iodide-promoted Debromination of Vicinal Dibromides. Part-I. In DMF

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The specific rate constants and the activation parameters $\Delta H^\ddagger$, $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger$, for the iodide-induced debromination reaction of *erythro*-2,3-dibromo-3-phenylpropanoic acids (*o*-Cl, -F, -Br, -NO₂, -CH₃; *m*-OCH₃, -F, -NO₂, -CH₃ and *p*-NO₂, -F, -Cl, -CH₃) and *erythro*-2,3-dibromobutanoic acid in dimethylformamide are reported. *Ortho*-substituted compounds were found to react faster than the unsubstituted ones irrespective of the nature of the substituent. Results indicate that the bromine attached to the α -carbon atom is attacked by I⁻ and the transition state is between non-synchronous nearly E1 type and synchronous E2 type.

AMONG the dehalogenation reactions, debromination of vicinal dibromides has been widely investigated¹. Since the first reported iodide-promoted debromination of coumarine dibromide², debromination of a wide variety of substrates ranging from the simple 1,2-diiodo- and dibromo-ethanes to the complex steroid dibromides have been carried out from the mechanistic/synthetic aspects. More than fifty reagents comprising of metals, cations and anions, including complexes have been used³⁻⁵. The overall process may be considered either as a nucleophilic attack on positive halogen or as a redox process involving two-electron reduction of the halide⁶. Both SN2-E2 and concerted E₂ mechanisms are reported⁷. Normally 1,2-dehalogenation in solution occurs in the *anti* mode, but *syn* dehalogenations are also known⁸. For *erythro* dibromides the reaction is stereospecific whereas for *threo* compounds it is stereoselective⁹. The overall iodide-induced debromination reaction is represented as,

Dehalogenation and decarboxylative elimination may accompany the dehalogenation of *erythro*-2,3-dibromo-3-phenylpropanoic acid depending on the conditions of the reaction, particularly the nature of the reagent^{10,11}. With iodide in ethanol or aqueous acetic acid, and with sodium acetylde in liquid ammonia it yielded *trans*-3-phenylpropanoic acid; with sodium ethoxide or hydroxide in liquid ammonia it gave the dehydrohalogenated product(s), while sodium hydroxide in water and acetone gave the decarboxylative dehydrohalogenation products, namely, *trans*- and *cis*-1-bromo-2-phenylethenes¹²⁻¹⁴.

In the case of *threo*-2,3-dibromo-3-phenylpropanoic acid, the debromination by iodide ion proceeded to only about 50% in protic media¹⁵.

Electron-attracting as well as electron-releasing substituents increased the rate of debromination of 1,2-dibromo-1,2-diphenylethanes¹⁶; while electron-attracting *p*-NO₂ and *m*-NO₂ substituents reduced the rate, electron-releasing *p*-OCH₃ group increased the rate in the substituted-*erythro*-2,3-dibromo-3-phenylpropanoic acids¹⁷. This paper deals with the iodide-promoted debromination of *erythro*-2,3-dibromo-3-phenylpropanoic acid (1), its substituted derivatives and *erythro*-2,3-dibromobutanoic acid (2) in dimethylformamide.

Experimental

Erythro-2,3-dibromo-3-phenylpropanoic acid, its various substituted derivatives (*o*-F, -Cl, -Br, -NO₂, -CH₃; *m*-F, -NO₂, -OCH₃, -CH₃ and *p*-NO₂, -F, -Cl, -CH₃) and *erythro*-2,3-dibromobutanoic acid were prepared by the addition of bromine to the corresponding unsaturated *trans*-acids in either chloroform or carbontetrachloride. The dibromides after crystallisation from toluene were checked for purity by melting point and gravimetric analysis of bromine present. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide purified by standard methods and reagent grade sodium iodide dried at 150° were used.

The extent of completion of the reaction was determined for all cases by estimating the liberated iodine volumetrically and was found to be 95 ± 2%. The product analysis showed the presence of only the corresponding unsaturated compound, and no dehydrobromination product could be detected. Kinetics were followed under second order conditions by estimating the liberated iodine volumetrically using 5 ml aliquots of the reaction mixture maintained at a suitable temperature. The specific rate constants were calculated using the rate equation,

$$k_2 = \frac{2.303}{t(b-3a)} \log \frac{a(b-3x)}{b(a-x)}$$

where, a is $[\text{substrate}]_0$ and b the $[\text{NaI}]_0$. Plots of t vs $\log a(b-3x)/b(a-x)$ were found to be linear indicating a second order. An excess of sodium iodide had to be used to convert the iodine to I_3^- . Kinetics were carried out at four different temperatures and at different concentration of the reactants in the range $1.0 \times 10^{-3} - 1.6 \times 10^{-2} M$ for the substrate and $1.3 \times 10^{-2} - 1.7 \times 10^{-1} M$ for sodium iodide. The mean second order rate constants were calculated; their average deviation being less than $\pm 3\%$. The k_a values are the mean of at least three runs.

Results and Discussion

Specific rate constants are presented in Table 1. The observed order of reactivity at 303 K for *para*- and *meta*-compounds is $p\text{-CH}_3 > \text{-F} > \text{-Cl} > \text{-H} > m\text{-OCH}_3 > \text{-F} > \text{-CH}_3 > p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2$. Both mesomeric and inductive effects are operative for *para*-substituted compounds, whereas for *meta*-compounds the inductive effect alone is

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON RATE CONSTANT* OF DEBROMINATION OF 1 ITS DERIVATIVES AND 2 IN DMF

Compd.	k_{298} $\times 10^3$	k_{303} $\times 10^3$	k_{308} $\times 10^3$	k_{313} $\times 10^3$	k_{318} $\times 10^3$
Compd. no. 1	—	5.19	8.54	13.7	22.2
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	2.87	4.68	7.70	11.9	—
<i>m</i> -F	2.95	4.00	7.80	12.1	—
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	—	3.59	6.18	10.3	—
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	—	4.55	6.98	11.3	—
<i>o</i> -F	5.04	7.92	14.0	21.4	—
<i>o</i> -Cl	4.35	7.06	12.0	18.6	—
<i>o</i> -Br	4.07	6.63	10.6	17.2	—
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	6.84	11.2	18.0	29.9	—
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	19.8	20.6	29.8	44.2	—
<i>p</i> -F	4.67	7.61	12.5	19.7	—
<i>p</i> -Cl	4.69	7.54	12.1	19.2	—
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	—	4.70	6.80	9.23	—
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	14.0	21.0	31.0	46.6	—
	k_{308} $\times 10^4$	k_{313} $\times 10^4$	k_{318} $\times 10^4$	k_{323} $\times 10^4$	
Compd. no. 2	1.25	2.08	3.32	5.25	

*dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹.

felt at the reaction centre. The *para*- and *ortho*-compounds are more reactive than the corresponding *meta*-compounds irrespective of the nature of the substituents, electron-donating or electron-withdrawing. The order $p\text{-F} > p\text{-Cl}$ indicates that with the decrease in the electron-attracting power of the substituent there is a decrease in the rate of the reaction and this trend, i.e. $p\text{-F} > p\text{-Cl} > p\text{-Br}$ is also observed in 2-propanol medium¹⁸.

The greater reactivity of *ortho* and *para* over *meta* in the methyl-substituted compounds is due to the hyperconjugative effect which reinforces the $+I$ effect on account of the conjugative stabilisation of the incipient double bond in the transition state. In the case of *o*- and *p*-NO₂ compounds on account of the $-I$ and $-M$ effect of the $-\text{NO}_2$ and $-\text{COOH}$ groups, both α - and β -bromine atoms become susceptible to the attack by the iodide ion. As the

$-\text{COOH}$ group is nearer to the reaction centre, the iodide ion attacks the α -bromine atom. Due to this, loosening of the $\text{C}_\beta\text{-Br}$ bond is inhibited by the $-\text{NO}_2$ group. If the attack is on the β -bromine the loosening of the $\text{C}_\alpha\text{-Br}$ bond is inhibited by the $-\text{COOH}$ group. This is the case with *p*-NO₂ compound, but when the $-\text{NO}_2$ group is in the *ortho*-position it interacts sterically with the β -bromine and accelerates the reactant towards the transition state thereby making it to react faster. In fact all the *ortho*-compounds have higher rates when compared to 1, irrespective of the nature of the substituent predominantly due to the spatial contribution. The order of reactivity of the *ortho*-compounds is $\text{CH}_3 > \text{NO}_2 > \text{F} > \text{Cl} > \text{Br}$.

According to Baciocchi¹⁶, the acceleration in rate of the iodide-induced debromination of substituted-*erythro*-1,2-dibromo-1,2-diphenylethanes by $-\text{NO}_2$ and $-\text{OCH}_3$ groups present in the *para*-position is due to the conjugative stabilisation of the developing double bond in the transition state; but in our case, *p*-NO₂ and *m*-OCH₃ are less reactive than 1, which is in agreement with the report in aqueous acetic acid¹⁵.

The activation parameters are given in Table 2. It can be seen that *p*-NO₂ and *m*-F compounds have the lowest and highest values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ respectively. The *o*- and *p*-CH₃ compounds react about 4.5 times faster than the *meta*, but have almost similar $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values. The *m*-OCH₃, $-\text{NO}_2$, *o*-F, $-\text{Cl}$, $-\text{Br}$, $-\text{NO}_2$ and *p*-F, $-\text{Cl}$ compounds have $\Delta H^\ddagger$ values in the range 68.0–72.0 kJ mol⁻¹ while *o*-F, $-\text{Cl}$ and $-\text{NO}_2$ compounds have nearly the same $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values as 1.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR DEBROMINATION OF 1, ITS DERIVATIVES AND 2 IN DMF AT 303 K

Compd.	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹
Compd. no. 1	72.8	44.4	86.2
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	69.5	56.1	86.6
<i>m</i> -F	80.8	19.3	86.6
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	68.8	58.3	86.9
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	69.4	88.3	86.7
<i>o</i> -F	71.6	45.2	85.0
<i>o</i> -Cl	71.2	47.3	85.4
<i>o</i> -Br	69.5	53.2	85.8
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	71.6	43.1	84.6
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	55.7	90.0	83.3
<i>p</i> -F	69.9	50.6	85.4
<i>p</i> -Cl	68.2	56.9	85.4
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	48.9	124	87.2
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	57.8	82.9	82.9
Compd. no. 2	76.6	72.0	98.8

Enthalpies of the reactants are lower than that of the product(s) olefins. The $\Delta H^\ddagger$ value reflects the extent of cleavage of the $\text{C}_\alpha\text{-Br}$ and $\text{C}_\beta\text{-Br}$ bonds and the formation of the π -bond between the carbon atoms. The degree of the double bond character varies synchronously with the progress in the rupture of the C-Br bonds for the various substituted compounds. The lesser the value of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ the greater is the double bond formation in

the transition state which implies a 'product like' transition state. The solvation effect of the dimethylformamide also plays a major role in the reaction. The lower the entropy of activation, the greater is the solvation of the transition state. The development of the double bond and the extent to which the bromine atoms are removed from the carbon determines their degree of solvation in the transition state.

In the case of *m*-F compound the substituent inductively withdraws electron density from the β -carbon thereby inhibiting the loosening of the C β -Br bond. This accounts for the highest value of $\Delta H^\ddagger$. The developing charge on the β -Br atom is decreased to a greater extent which results in the lesser solvation of the transition state leading to the high value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$. The lower $\Delta H^\ddagger$ value of the *m*-NO $_2$ compound when compared with the former, can be ascribed to the polar aprotic solvent which solvates the NO $_2$ group resulting in reduction of its electron-withdrawing capacity. The low values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for the *p*-NO $_2$ compound indicate that the transition state is more 'product like', where extended conjugation is possible and greater solvation also takes place. In electron-donating substituents like *o*-, *p*- and *m*-CH $_3$, the incipient charge on the β -Br is reinforced and more solvent molecules are frozen around it; hence the lower $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ values. A linear variation of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ with $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is observed and their values more or less compensate to make the $\Delta G^\ddagger$ values remain nearly the same. The isokinetic temperature 353.6 K with a correlation coefficient of 0.979 shows that the same mechanism is operating in all the cases. The relative rates of the various reactants also reflect to a certain extent on the thermodynamic stabilities of the olefinic products.

From Table 1 it is seen that **1** reacts about 10 times faster than **2** at 308 K. The lower $\Delta G^\ddagger$ and $\Delta H^\ddagger$ values of **1** as compared to **2** is a clear indication of the stabilisation of the incipient double bond between the carbon atoms by conjugative release of electron density by the phenyl ring.

The effect of substituents on any reaction is generally assessed by a study of the Hammett plot. The plots of $\log k$ vs σ , and $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs σ° were not linear, but $\log k$ vs σ^+ plots shows a better correlation with a coefficient of 0.93. The regression coefficient ρ having a value of -0.91 indicates that the substituents in the phenyl ring do not play a major role in the reactivity.

Of the two possibilities of attack by iodide on the bromine atom attached to the α - and β -carbon atoms, preferential attack on the α -bromine by iodide occurs when electron-attracting substituents are present in the phenyl ring. Electron-releasing substituents aid the departure of β -Br as Br $^-$. The reverse should occur if the attack is on β -bromine; but in our study, it is seen that the

rate is increased by electron-releasing and electron-attracting substituents in the *ortho*-position, and *para*-compounds are found to be more reactive than the corresponding *meta*-compounds.

The effect of substituents in the debromination reaction bears no resemblance with the E2 H dehydrobromination of 2-phenylethylbromide by bases^{1,2} and is similar to that of the ethoxide ion promoted decarboxylative debromination of the anion of substituted-cinnamic acid dibromides^{1,3}. Different degrees of double bond character are manifested in the transition state based on the extent to which the C-Br bonds are cleaved. So in the debromination, the transition state should lie between non-synchronous nearly E1 type and synchronous E2 type and the mechanism may be represented as

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